

Unlocking Access through the OpenAccess Button Custom Link, presented at the EBSCO User Group Meeting in San Antonio, TX, October 25, 2019

Sharon Whitfield and Melissa A. Hofmann, Rider University Libraries

We presented Rider University's experience implementing the Open Access Button (<https://openaccessbutton.org/>) custom link in EBSCO's Discovery Service (EDS) and in our EBSCOHost databases. In 2019, Rider University Libraries (RUL) implemented a new strategic plan that focused on increasing awareness of open access (OA) resources. One mechanism to carry out the strategic plan was for RUL to implement the Open Access Button via an EDS custom link. RUL chose the Open Access Button over other extensions or APIs because the Open Access Button makes the author's role in OA more visible. The Open Access Button link appears in EDS anytime the article is not available in full text. If the item is not available via open access after clicking on the custom link, the patron may then contact the author through the Open Access Button interface to request that the article be made available legally through open access, according to publisher stipulations. The Open Access Button facilitates this process by mediating the request between the author and requestor and in some cases archiving the content for the author (<https://blog.openaccessbutton.org/making-more-research-open-access-one-paper-at-a-time-25b95cd36c8f>).

During the conference, we reported that in a period of nine months RUL patrons clicked on the Open Access Button custom link in our EDS over 680 times and were able to successfully retrieve the open article 17% of the time. Additional benefits reported were interlibrary loan cost savings, which were \$1115-\$2030. Anecdotal benefits consisted of increased patron awareness of OA--as the prominence of the link in EDS and our EBSCOHost databases forced librarians to teach the purpose and use of the Open Access Button during instruction sessions and reference encounters, RUL patrons taking an active part in the open access movement by requesting articles, and strategic plan objectives being met.

We also reported some drawbacks, one of which was the low rate of success when using the Open Access Button: will students stop using the tool if they hit too many dead ends? Another obstacle is the lack of recovery from the Open Access Button page, which opens in a new tab and whose relationship to the library is unclear. It would be beneficial if there were a mechanism to easily return back to the library page or customized messaging to instruct users locally when the article is not available in open access. The text of error messages were also a concern. For example, students were confused by the "Someone has requested access to the article" message. Without library instruction, students did not know what their next steps should be, such as requesting to be notified when the article is made available, returning to the EDS citation page to fill out the linked Interlibrary Loan form, or both. We will begin working with EBSCO and OpenAccess to figure out what can be done to alleviate the lack of recovery and to have clearer error messages and local direction. It would be interesting to track how many of our students request items from the author, how many of those articles are filled and in what publication state (pre- or postprint), and in what time frame, and to compare this with ILL requests. The hope is that as RUL patrons and others continue to request that authors make their publications available, the amount of OA materials in the information landscape will increase.